

NOMINALIZATION AS A DEFINITE PROCESS IN JAPANESE

Hagiu A.

PhD Student

Bucharest, University of Bucharest, Faculty of Foreign Languages,
Department of English Applied Linguistics**Abstract**

The purpose of this article is to discuss the process of nominalization in Japanese as a marker of definiteness that is highly peculiar to an articleless language like this language. The topic includes different branches of nominalizations like clausal or phrasal nominalizations, but the area of debate spans across hundreds of pages. As a matter of fact, we will resort only to the lexical characterization of nominalizations in Japanese. They are a highly structured lexeme which include two nouns cojoined with a Genitive particle in order to form a cohesive Noun Phrase. Nominalizations can be assimilated to Genitive structures in English, in the form of N1+ *OF*+N2, but these structures usually suggest the possessive character of a Noun. In Japanese, the employment of such structures is usually much broader.

Keywords: Nominalization, Japanese, Particles, Lexicality, Topic Definiteness, Genitive Structures, Noun Phrase.

A typical Japanese NP is formed out of a noun as the head of a phrase together with zero (\emptyset) or more dependent constituents of various types as its adnominal. The relative position and order of a dependent adnominal is a typological parameter, on which an NP turns on. The adnominal constituents in an NP vary in structure and function, which are of four types: morphological, lexical, phrasal, and clausal, of which the morphological one tends to be a smaller, while the clausal one tends to be a larger one (Givon, 2001:1-3).

From this point of view, some may argue that syntactic phenomena in Japanese is hazardous. However, we deny this thesis and show that nominalization is a means of obtaining definite interpretation in Japanese and it is syntactically driven. For example, in this paper I will bring into discussion two types of nominalization that occur in Japanese, namely the lexical nominalization as a relevant dichotomy. The clausal nominalization will be dealt with very briefly as a matter of similarity with the lexical one, since the topic expands across several pages.

The nominalization processes that operate on lexical forms are the grammatical processes of conversion and derivation at the lexical level, while those that operate on the sentences are dual processes of transformation and derivation and reduction in certain causal properties of clauses at the sentence level. In this regard, we can derive different types of NMLs by investigating the nominalization processes operating over different kinds of NLZs with the support of necessary linguistic evidence (Chen, 2013). These grammatical processes are conversion and derivation which operate over the words other than the noun, i.e. verb and adjective at the lexical level and bring forth lexical NMLs.

Clausal nominalizations come as the result of the SOV structure of Japanese since they require noun as determinants. Additionally, one can derive Nominal clauses by investigating the dual processes of transformation, and derivation and reduction in certain clausal properties of clauses operating over the NLZs at the sentence with the support of linguistic evidence. In this phase, we accumulated all the yields of the nominalization including Lexical NMLs and ANCs, and Nominal

clauses, which are as good as Noun and good enough to partake in the formation of NPs. Then, in the second, i.e. last phase, we showed how each of the lexical NMLs, ANCs, and nominal clauses either as a Head or as an Adnominal partake in the formation of NPs with the support of linguistic data. The existence of both lexical and clausal nominalizations is an indication that nominalization represents a genuine linguistic process and is not hazardous.

Lexical nominalization is a productive process, by means of which a word belonging to other than the noun class yields a derivative noun as in the constituent with or without some morphological adjustment. It is relatively less productive in Japanese as compared to that in English. Nishio (1961) found only 30% -40% of verbs can be transformed into deverbal NMLs. Hanna (2018:43) offers a new analysis of Japanese nominalization that distinguishes between lexical and grammatical nominalizations on one hand, and between verbal-based nominalizations and nominal-based nominalizations on the other. Formal nouns like `koto` and `no` partake in this operation. These processes yield the Noun Phrase definite

(1) Sekai-no ugoki-o yomi nasai.

*N.World, PART.Gen., N.Movement, PART.Acc., V.I
MPER.Read*

Read the trends in the world.

(Horie, 1997:45)

(2) Gakubutchoo tosite-no sekinin-no omosa-o keikensita.

*N.School, N.Dean, PREP.Regarding, PART.Gen.,
N.Responsibility, PART.Gen., N.Importance, PART.Acc.V.PAST.Ex
perienceI*

I experienced the importance of Dean's overall responsibility.

(Hanna, 2018:51)

(3) Nero-ga rooma-o hakai sita koto-wa zizitu-da.

*N.Nero, TOP., N.Roma, PART.Acc., N.Destruction,
V.PAST.Do, N.Thing, TOP., N.Fact, V.Be*

Nero's destruction of Rome is a fact.
(Horie, 1997:48)

(4) *yama-ni iku yori umi-ni iku hoo-ga ii*
N.Moun-
tain,PART.Dat.,V.Go,PREP.Than,N.Sea,PART.Dat.,V.
Go,TOP.,Adj.Good

It is better to go to the sea than to go to the mountains.

(Horie, 1997: 51)

(5) *Ken wa [[Sai ga motte kita]NMLZ no]NP o*
tabeta.

N.Ken, TOP., N.Sai, TOP., V.PAST.Bring, PART.NO
M., PART.Acc., V.PAST.Eat

Ken ate what Sai brought.

(Hanna, 2018: 64)

In the examples above we notice an instance of a nominalizer being transformed into a Noun Phrase by means of the genitive particle `no` adjoining the accusative particle `o` which should have introduced the direct object clause.

Another interesting instance of lexical nominalizations is that which includes relative clauses. Even though some may argue against categorizing relatives as part of lexical nominalizations, they are classified as such by authors like Simpson (2003), who bring into discussion eloquent sentences. This is mainly because relatives, as shown above, lack the relative pronoun and are obtained by means of adjoining two nouns or two clauses. This allows for lexical interpretation of the phenomenon under the process of nominalization.

Even though relatives are already definite by nature, since they provide a plus of semantic content nominalizing them contributes even further to the definite character of the Noun Phrase. In Japanese it is well-known that subjects in relative clauses may appear in either nominative or genitive case, as in (6), this being commonly referred to as *ga/no* conversion:

(6) *Taroo-ga/-no katta hon.*
N.Taroo-NOM/-GEN, V:Past.Buy, N.Book
'the book that Taroo bought'

Some authors have tried to provide a syntactic foundation for this phenomenon, namely to prove that indeed lexical nominalizations are not hazardously formed, but they are part of a linguistic mechanism to render the syntagm definite, for example, to find restrictions (privative features) or any other sorts of principles that limit or allow the occurrence of lexical nominalizations within relatives. Simpson (2008:146) compared Korean to Japanese and found that in addition to the thematic 'possessor' restriction in modern Korean, it is also not possible for a genitive subject in modern Korean relative clauses to be preceded by an adverb such as *ecey* 'yesterday' which refers to the action of the relative clause, as in (7). This comes in sharp contrast to modern Japanese where a sentential adverb may indeed precede a genitive subject, as shown in (8):

(7) [*ecey John-i/*John-uy sa-n*]-chayk

Adv.Yesterday, N.John-NOM/John-
GEN, V:Past.Buy-N, N.Book

'The book that John bought yesterday.'

(Shigeko, 1991:20)

(8) [*kinoo Hanako-no katta*] *hon-wa Bottyan desu*
Adv.Yesterday, N.Hanako-

GEN, V:Past.Buy, N.Book-TOP, N.Bottyan, V:Pres.Be

'The book which Hanako bought yesterday is Botchan.'

(Matsumoto, 1997:6)

Previously however, this relation of the genitive DP to the relative clause head-noun/ NP appears to have been unrestricted, and it is clearly unrestricted in modern Japanese, so a natural question now is to ask how the un/restricted distinction between modern Korean and middle Korean/modern Japanese should be captured.

One possible route of explanation in the analysis of Shibatani (2009) is to pursue the connection between gerund-type nominalizations and the occurrence of genitive subjects in relative clauses. It is well-known that nominalizations of certain types cross-linguistically license thematically-unrestricted genitive subjects. This is seen in English gerunds and Korean type III gerund nominalizations and also in a number of nominalizations formed with *no* in Japanese, as for example in (9) and (10), (9) being a simple clausal nominalization, (10) a pseudo-cleft type structure also formed with the element *no* and allowing for optional genitive case on the subject in place of nominative:

(9) *Hanako-ga [Taroo-no tsuita] no-o mita*
Hanako-

N.Hanako, NOM, N.Taroo-
GEN, V:Past.Arrive, NOM., ACC, V:Past.See
'Hanako saw Taroo arrive.'

(10) [*Taroo-no katta*] *no-wa hon desu*
N.Taroo-

GEN, V:Past.NOM., TOP., N.Book. V:Pres.Be
'What Taroo bought was a book.'

The syntactic process at stake here is argued by Shibatani (2009) in terms of syntactic derivation. He assumes that the nominalizer *no* here is a functional head of type D0, and that it can be suggested that the subjects in (9) and (10) have their genitive case licensed/checked directly in SpecDP by the nominalizer particle *no* (either overtly or at LF; in either case it may be assumed that the genitive case-marker *no* is attached to the subject DP as an inflectional suffix in the lexicon, in line with the current Minimalist views). Because there is no 'head' N(P) in such pure nominalizations, there will be no possessor-like semantic restrictions on genitive subjects and genitive subjects will be thematically-unrestricted, as noted by him. Another interesting phenomenon regarding relative clauses in Japanese is that of temporal interpretation of the verb, which is triggered by the presence of a relative clause.

According to Shibatani (2009), Japanese used to have special adnominal morphology in its relative

clauses, verbs appearing in the attributive form with suffixes which contrasted with the conclusive forms of other clauses. This system of opposition is well documented as having later got restructured into a general tense system which then did not manifest any difference between matrix and subordinate clauses (see e.g. Shibatani 1996, Takeuchi 1998). Reason to believe that there may not have been necessary re-analysis into a full tense system inside relative clauses is the interesting fact that the 'past tense' morpheme in relative clauses in fact need not always result in a past time meaning and can instead correspond simply to perfective/ completive aspect which is fully compatible with a future reading, as seen in (11) from Tohru (2012):

(11). [Ashita ichiban hayaku kita] hito-ni kore-o ageru

*Adv.Tomorrow, Adv.most
early, V:Past.Come, N.Person-DAT, Pron.This-ACC, V:Pres.Give*

'I will give this to the person who comes (lit. came) first tomorrow.'

This future-oriented interpretation of the past tense morpheme is restricted to relative clauses and therefore suggests that re-analysis of attributive and conclusive forms as tense may still be optional in this environment (Shibatani, 2009:152). The syntactic endeavors of the author are aimed at providing a scientific foundation for the phenomenon of relative clauses analyzed as lexical nominalizations.

Simpson (2008) finds a second possible way of accounting for the unrestricted genitive case available for Japanese relative clause subjects which might be to suggest that when the posited attributive form nominalizer became re-analyzed into the tense system, the nominalizer position might not have simply disappeared but instead may have been retained and occupied by a new null nominalizer element. Elsewhere where the attributive form was re-analyzed and its hypothetical nominalizer status was lost, a new overt nominalizer was in fact inserted in a renewal process common in language development:

(12) [te tatake-ba yababiko-no kotauru] ito urusai.
N.Hand, V.Clap-as, N.Echo-

GEN, N.Answer.ADN, Adv.Very, Adj.Annoying

'It is very annoying that there is an echo when he claps his hands.'

(Genji monogatari, 11thC)

(13) [te-o tatakū-to kodama-ga kotaeru] no-wa taihen huyukai-da.

N.Hand-ACC., V.Clap, Prep.When, N.Echo-NOM, V.Answer, NO-TOP, Adv.very Adj.Annoying, V.Pres.Be

'It is very annoying that there is an echo when he claps his hands.'

(Tsujimura, 2007:52)

Shibatani (2009) demonstrated that the structural and functional adjustment of a finite clause occurred through the elimination or reduction of some sentential

properties like illocutionary and modal properties from the sentence. Baker (2011) proved that nominalization existed in degree in a clause-like constituent in the cline of desententialization of *Sakha*. Hence, the clausal nominalization brings forth two different types of NML constituents depending on the extent of reduction of clausal properties from a finite clause (sentence) as it undergoes the nominalization process. The complete nominalization at the syntactic level involves the simultaneous process of derivation and transformation, which yields an ANC, i.e. NP with the derivative verbal noun on its head (NML-3). On the other hand, the partial clausal nominalization involves the reduction of certain clausal functions of the clause to transform a finite clause into a dependent clause (NML-4).

The denotation of the *no*-headed part is determinate in two respects. Firstly, as shown in (40), it is determinate with regard to the definiteness of the denotation, meaning that it renders the lexeme definite, turning it from adjective to noun. Secondly, it is determinate in that it shows syntactic restrictions. The example are borrowed from Seraku (2012:8):

(14) [Akai no]-o Tom-ga nagu-tta.
[red NO]-ACC Tom-NOM hit-PAST
'Tom hit a/the red one.'

Makino (1968: p.51) observes that *no* cannot stand on its own. Compare (202) with (203):

(15) * No-o Tom-ga nagu-tta.
NO-ACC Tom-NOM hit-PAST

Makino considers only participant nominalization, but it is also true of situation nominalization. (204) should be compared with (202).

(16) * No-o Tom-ga shi-tteiru.
NO-ACC Tom-NOM know-PRES

These data are amenable to my analysis. The entry of *no* requires that a proposition should have been constructed before the parse of *no*. Formally, this requirement is expressed in the two IF-clauses in the entry of *no* in depicted by Seraku (2012). In (15, 16), however, no items precede *no* in the strings, and a parser cannot build up a proposition before processing *no*. These data show there are syntactic operations at stake. The semantic structure of the nominalized adjective in (17) is provided in the next section, where Seraku (ibidem.) argues that *Akai no* yields the epsilon term:

(17) $(\epsilon, x, P(x) \& akai'(x))$

Secondly, since the content of the *no*-headed part is determinate, it is pragmatically inferred that a speaker has in mind a specific entity, say, a red person, the term (17) may be enriched as (18), where *hito*' is the content of *hito/person* (Seraku, ibidem.)

(18) $(\epsilon, x, P(x) \& [akai'(x) \& hito'(x)])$

It is well known that if the *no*-headed part denotes a human in participant nominalization, derogatory expressivity is observed (Kitagawa, 2005: p.1259). Consider (1, 2, 3), repeated here as (207, 208, 209); expressivity is found in participant nominalization (207, 209a), but not in situation nominalization (208, 209b).

(19) [Akai no]-o Tom-ga nagu-tta.
[red NO]-ACC Tom-NOM hit-PAST
'Tom hit a/the red one.'

(20) [Mary-ga kireina no]-o Tom-ga shi-tteiru.
[Mary-NOM beautiful NO]-ACC Tom-NOM
know-PRES
'Tom knows that Mary is beautiful.'

(21) [Nai-ta no]-o Tom-ga mi-ta.
[cry-PAST NO]-ACC Tom-NOM see-PAST
a. 'Tom saw someone who cried.'
b. 'Tom saw the event of someone's having cried.'

What has not been reported in the literature is that expressivity is not always derogatory. To take (21) as an example, if the denoted person's face turns red after a pint of beer and the speaker hits the person in jest, expressivity may be "affectionate familiarity with the denoted person". Any adequate account of *no* must model this context-dependency of expressivity (Yuji Nishiyama, p.c.).

To account for the above data, it is usually posited the constraint that the indefinite denotation of the *no*-headed part should be an object (rather than a human), the idea being that if the *no*-headed part denotes a human, definiteness emerges through pragmatic inference: It is predicted that if the *no*-headed part denotes a non-human, definiteness should be absent:

(22) [Akai no]-o Tom-ga tabe-ta.
[red NO]-ACC Tom-NOM eat-PAST
'Tom ate a/the red one.'

However, this is not the case, since the employment of clausal nominalization structures shows constraints only syntactically. Moreover, what becomes evident is that those structures accept demonstrative pronouns, which are inherently definite and which only adhere to definite Noun Phrases:

(23) Sono [akai no]-o Tom-ga nagu-tta.
that [red NO]-ACC Tom-NOM hit-PAST
'Tom hit that red one.'

Conclusions of This Article

Nominalizations have been shown to represent one of the main means of expressing definiteness in Japanese, along with the employment of classifiers and adjuncts. This is due to the fact, that, unlike European languages, in Japanese there is a complex process which includes both clauses, nouns, adjectives and relatives partaking in nominalizations. Moreover, the process requires the involvement of a highly specialized lexeme, the nominalizing particle *NO*, which, to-

gether with the Accusative particle „*O*” and the topical particle „*WA*”, form nominalized sentences. This section was meant to describe nominalization as a definite process, which branches into two parts, namely the lexical nominalization and the clausal nominalization, both of which are complex.

In order to demonstrate that nominalizations are not a hazardous phenomenon, I endeavored to bring into discussion different syntactic processes that are at stake, namely that of blocking effects for suffixes on nouns and adjectives in Japanese, as well as genitive subjects being preceded or not by adverb as a criteria for the grammaticality of nominalized lexical constructions. In Shibatani's study (2009) these criteria are fruitful and have been illustrated with due care. In studying the research data, I used the sharing method in which the main tool was to bring into discussion different data and to demonstrate that definiteness can be expressed even in articleless languages. The direct element-sharing technique was to divide elements that directly shape the phenomenon of nominalization and then analyze these parts separately (Makino, 1968). The technique was applied by dividing words attached by the nominalizing particle *no* and studying the resulting syntactic mechanisms.

Based on data analysis as explained above, it can be concluded that nominalizing particle *no* attached to noun serves as a modifier of the main noun. Besides, it changes the internal structure from a single word into a noun phrase. The same happens with classifiers, which form a whole NP by adjoining the numeral and the functional item. The word which serves as a modifier is usually not limited to one word, but it can be more than one word, a cluster of words in lexical nominalizations, an adjective or even a clause as illustrated in clausal nominalizations. Because nominalizations form whole NPs, it is easily understood that they are definite by nature. For clausal nominalizations, the nominalizing particle *no* in data above is used for nominalizing the verbal clause. A verbal clause is attached by the nominalizing particle *no* and changes its internal structure into a noun phrase. The Noun phrase then occupies the syntactic function as a topic in the sentence because it is marked by particle *wa*, thus operating a process that renders it definite.

References

1. Baker, M. C. (2011). Degree of nominalization: Clause-like constituents in Sakha. *Lingua* 121 (7), 1164-1193.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lingua.2011.01.012>
2. Chen, S. 2013. On the Levels of the Independence of Japanese Infinitive-derived Nouns. Proceedings of the 4th Corpus Japanese Studies Workshop. National Japanese Language Institute (September 2013).
3. Comrie, B., & Thompson, S. A. (1985). Lexical nominalization. In T. Shopen (Eds.), *Language Typology and Syntactic Description* (pp. 334-381), Cambridge University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511618437.006>
4. Dixon, R. M. W. (2006). Complementation clauses and complementation strategies in typological perspective. In R.M.W. Dixon & A. Aikhenvald (Eds.),

Complementation: A cross-linguistic typology. Oxford University Press.

5. Givon, T. (2001). *Syntax* (Vol II). John Benjamins.

6. Halle, M., & Marantz, A. (1993). Distributed morphology and the pieces of inflection. In K. Halle & S. J. Keyser (Eds.), *The view from building* (pp. 111-176), MIT Press.

7. Hanna, K. (2018). Nominalization and Adjectivization by Japanese Suffixes: -sa, -sei, -na, and -teki. *Proceedings of AJL (The Asian Junior Linguists Conference)*

8. Horie, K. (1997). Three types of nominalization in modern Japanese: No, koto, and zero. *Linguistics* 35 (5), 879-894.

<https://doi.org/10.1515/ling.1997.35.5.879>

9. Nishio, T. (1961). A study on the nominalization of continuative verb forms. *Kokugogaku*. 43

15. Okamoto, Shigeo, 1991. Nominal 'tautologies' in Japanese: X wa A'. X ga A', and X lylo X. *Proceedings of the 17th Annual Meeting of the Berkeley Linguistics Society*, 2 I S-229.

16. Matsumoto, Y. 1997. Noun-modifying constructions in Japanese: A frame-semantic approach. John Benjamins.

17. Shibatani, M. 2009. Elements of complex structures, where recursion isn't: The case of relativization. In T. Givon & M. Shibatani, (Eds.), *Syntactic complexity: Diachrony, acquisition, neuro-cognition, evolution* (pp. 163-198). John Benjamins.

18. Tohoru, S. (2012). Two types of nominalization in Japanese as an outcome of semantic tree growth. *Proceedings of the 26th Pacific Asia Conference on Language, Information and Computation, PACLIC 2012*, (i), 153-162.